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Investigation of Factors Affecting Pre-School Teachers' Vocational Alienation*

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Abstract

Preschool teachers have an important place in achieving the goals of preschool education and in assuring its quality. Since vocational alienation affect preschool teachers' performance negatively, main purpose of this study is to investigate factors affecting their vocational alienation. For this purpose 227 pre-school teachers from Turkey voluntarily participated in the study. The model of the study was correlational survey model. Research data was collected with; Personal Information Form, Vocational Alienation Scale for the Preschool Teachers (VAS-PT), Organizational Climate Scale and Preschool Teachers' Self-Efficacy Beliefs Scale. According to teachers' graduation degree variable, the vocational alienation scale scores of teachers at the graduate level differed statistically negatively from other groups (high school, associate degree, undergraduate). The scores of the sub-dimensions of the scale of vocational alienation of the group consisting of teachers who have a different vocation they want to do, differ negatively compared to other colleagues. Between teachers' vocational alienation scores and self-efficacy beliefs and organizational climate scores, positive and negative significant relationships were determined. There were significant negative relationships between teachers' vocational alienation scores and all sub-dimensions of the Self-Efficacy Belief Scale. Negative relationships were determined among the scores of all sub-dimensions of Vocational Alienation Scale for Pre-school Teachers and "Supportive Principle Behavior," "Intimate Teacher Behavior" and "Collaborative Teacher Behavior among Colleagues" of the Organizational Climate Scale. In addition, there were positive relationships between "Disengaged Teacher Behavior" and "Restrictive Principle Behavior" dimensions of Organizational Climate Scale and all sub-dimensions of Vocational Alienation Scale for Pre-school Teachers.

Keywords: Preschool Teachers, Vocational Alienation, Self-Efficacy, Organizational Climate

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1. Introduction

The quality of pre-school education in Turkey is not in a satisfactory level; for this reason, education of teachers comes to the forefront (Atay-Turhan, Koç, Isıksal, & Isıksal, 2009). Investments aimed at enhancing the quality of pre-school education offer many benefits such as increase in children's elementary school scores, decrease in grade repetitions, and less need for special education (Lynch and Vaghul, 2015). The teacher as an important part of pre-school education holds a significant position in reaching the goals and the desired quality of education. As they help build the society, teachers should be educated in a way to meet the needs of present day (Kösterioğlu and Kösterioğlu, 2008). A better qualified teacher means better learned students and a more permanent learning (Karacaoğlu, 2008). Apart from good qualifications, teachers should also be aware of their strengths and have confidence of self-efficacy.

Self-efficacy is the teacher's belief in that they will make a change in the student's behaviors and academic success (Guo, Justice, Sawyer and Tompkins, 2011). Individuals who believe that they will be successful in a given duty are more successful than those who do not (Bandura, 1986, 1997). According to Bandura (1986), teachers' perception of self-efficacy can be influenced and shaped by various school factors (Guo, Piasta, Justice, & Kaderavek 2010; Hoy & Woolfolk, 1993; Raudenbush, Rowan, & Cheong, 1992; Ross, Cousins, & Gadalla, 1996). Pre-school teachers' self-efficacy beliefs are important in order to enhance class quality and to support children's academic success (Guo et al., 2010; Justice, Mashburn, Hamre, and Pianta, 2008). Teachers' perception of self-efficacy may indirectly influence student success thanks to the quality communication they establish with students (Goddard and Goddard, 2001). A study conducted by Wolter and Daugherty (2007) shows that teachers' teaching qualifications such as experience and holding a degree can impact their perception of self-efficacy. According to another study, there is a statistically significant and positive correlation between teachers' self-efficacy beliefs and job satisfaction (Infurna, Riter, and Schultz, 2018). Another study conducted with pre-school teachers shows that inclusion of teachers in the decision-making process and their cooperation with co-workers as they perceive it are related to their self-efficacy (Guo, Justice, Sawyer and Tompkins, 2011). In other words, there is a correlation between organizational climate and teacher self-efficacy.

Organizational climate is a point to be emphasized since it affects organizational behavior (Akbaba-Altun and Memişoğlu, 2011). According to Pidarta, organizational climate is characteristics that can affect the behaviors of organization members that make an organization different from others (Waruwu, 2015). According to Yılmaz and Altinkurt (2013), organizational climate is the general working atmosphere and feelings of the environment that consist of employees' relations and behaviors. The factors used to explain organizational climate are the characteristics of the working environment, perceptions of the employees, their behaviors as a result of their perceptions and distinctive characteristics of an organization (Gök, 2009). What can be said about school as an organization and school climate is in parallel with organizational climate. When organizational climate is applied to education, it is defined as some psycho-social characteristics that people working at school use to describe and interpret their working environment (Hoy and Miskel, 2008). According to Conley (2006), school climate is the working atmosphere where perceptions and conditions about organizational factors form the spirits of employees and the leadership style of the administrator. While the factors affecting school climate vary in literature (Qian, Jiang, and Ruan, 2007 as cited in Jiang, Li, Wang and Li, 2019; Xiaofu and Qiwen, 2007; Tschannen-Moran and Hoy, 1997 as cited in Hu, Li, Wang, Reynolds and Wang, 2019), Hoy et al. handled it in two main headings as the principal's behaviors and coworkers' behaviors and six sub-headings as (a) supportive principal behavior: they are open to suggestions, their criticism is constructive and supportive, (b) commanding principal behavior: autocratic administrator who has a strict and tight administration, (c) restrictive principal behavior: they assign unnecessary workload to teachers and are preventive rather than supportive, (d) cooperative teacher behavior: they are respectful to each other's professionalism and support each other's progress, (e) intimate teacher behavior: they establish strong social bonds and become friends, (f) disengaged teacher behavior: they have negative attitude and criticize their colleagues (Hoy & Miskel 2010 as cited in Yılmaz & Altinkurt, 2013).

Studies conducted to reveal the relationship between school climate and job satisfaction concluded that there is a significant positive relationship between the two (Hoy & Miskel, 2008). Teachers' positive perceptions of organizational climate are related to job satisfaction and thus the quality of education (Ghavifekr & Pillia, 2016).

Organizations with employees with higher job satisfaction have higher productivity (Robbins, 2007 as cited in Waruwu, 2015). Xiafu and Qiwen (2007) found a positive statistically significant relationship between school climate and job satisfaction, while a statistically negative relationship was found between school climate and management, materials and salaries. They argue that teachers' satisfaction with their salaries is affected by good management and the teaching environment. It is also revealed that principal behavior and school organizational climate are correlated in this study. Principal behaviors, relationship with colleagues, school climate and self-efficacy beliefs mentioned in the literature may cause the individual to feel belonging to the environment they are in. In other words, all the factors listed may cause the teacher to become alienated from the teaching profession.

Aldemir defines "alienation" as the belief of the person about to what extent what they do for the results they want to achieve can be effective in achieving the intended results (Çalışır, 2006). Seeman (1959), who has pioneering studies in this field in the literature, proposes to consider alienation by the personal stance of the person in society, and discusses alienation in five categories. These categories are (a) powerlessness: feeling powerless in the face of rule makers and rules and the thought of not being able to change things, (b) meaninglessness: inability to make sense of the causes and consequences of their own and others' behaviors and finding the world too complex to set a goal (Mackey, 1974 as cited in Sanberk, 2003); (c) normlessness: believing that the social rules are broken or that they are no longer functional, (d) sense of isolation: the individual abstracts themselves from their physical environment and avoids communication (Kıhrı, 2013), (e) self-alienation: according to Mills, the person thinks that they are serving something foreign to them and alienates themselves as a result of this thought (Seeman, 1959). In some literature studies, alienation is considered as an indicator of burnout (Halaçoğlu, 2009).

Vocational alienation can be defined as the employee finds their job meaningless and does not get satisfaction from work relations and sees themselves as an insignificant element of the system (Elma, 2003). Hoy, Blazovsky and Newland define vocational alienation as a reflection of the feelings created by disappointment of the individual with working conditions in the organization (as cited in Elma, 2003). Such a person does not consider their job as a part of their life, denying the position and dignity that the organization has given them (Eryılmaz, 2010). There are many reasons for vocational alienation listed in the literature. The following are listed among the factors that cause vocational alienation: negative behaviors of principles and employees, cooperation between the subordinate and the superior, the feeling of loneliness of the individual, artificial, temporary and superficial relationships (Şimşek, Çelik, Akgemici, & Fettahoğlu, 2006), organizational climate (Celep, 2008), closed organizational climate, bureaucratic structure (Eryılmaz, 2010) and commitment to the organization (Minibaş, 1993). It has been discovered in the studies that the less the commitment of the employees to the organization or the job is, the more alienated they are from their job (Minibaş, 1993). Ulrich has listed the factors that will increase the commitment of employees to the profession and reduce their vocational alienation as cooperation, teamwork, common achievements, communication and interest in people (Kıhrı, 2013). As there are many reasons for vocational alienation, a study can be done for each reason to eliminate these reasons. Eryılmaz (2010) has stated one of them to be ensuring the participation of employees in management. In the light of the literature, it is possible to say that the organizational climate of the employees, their colleagues and the administrator's attitudes are important factors in vocational alienation. In this regard, there may be a relationship between teachers' vocational alienation and their perceptions of organizational climate and self-efficacy. When the literature is examined, it is seen that studies on this subject are very limited, especially studies conducted on pre-school teachers. Hence, the relationship between pre-school teachers' vocational alienation and their perceptions of organizational climate and self-efficacy is decided to be investigated in this study at first. Secondly, the relationship between some variables (gender, graduation degree, years of experience, desire for a career change, class size, weekly working hours and types of educational institutions that teachers work) and teachers' vocational alienation level was also examined within the scope of this study. Research questions were as follows:

- Is there a significant relationship between preschool teachers' level of vocational alienation and their perceptions of organizational climate and self-efficacy?
- Do pre-school teachers' level of vocational alienation differ significantly according to variables such as gender, graduation degree, years of experience, desire for a career change, class size, weekly working hours, types of educational institutions

2. Method

2.1 Research Model

In this study, a relational screening model was used to examine pre-school teachers' level of vocational alienation in terms of different variables and to determine the relationship between their self-efficacy belief, organizational climate and their level of vocational alienation. Screening models generally handle the opinions and attitudes of individuals in large groups about a phenomenon or an event, and thus they try to describe facts and events (Karakaya, 2009). As for the relational screening model, it tries to determine the existence of a relationship between two or more variables or the degree of the relationship (Karasar, 2014).

2.2 Study Group

The study group of this research consists of 227 pre-school teachers who work in pre-school education institutions during the academic year of 2019-2020. Table 1 shows the demographic information about pre-school teachers taking part in the study.

Table 1: Demographic information of the participants

		f	%
Gender	Female	218	96
	Male	9	4
Graduation Degree	High School	9	4
	Associates Degree	31	14
	Bachelor's	163	72
	Postgraduate	24	10
School Type	State Kindergarten	102	45
	State Independent Kindergarten	63	28
	Private Kindergarten	62	27
Years of Experience	5 years and less	95	42
	6-10 years	60	26
	11-15 years	42	19
	16- 20 years	22	10
	21 years or more	8	3
Weekly Working Hours	20-30 hours	133	58
	31-40 hours	54	24
	41 hours or more	40	18
Class Size	0-10 children	22	10
	11-20 children	147	64
	21-30 children	50	22
	31 or more	8	4
Desire for a Career Change	Yes	78	34
	No	149	66

It is observed that the majority of the participants are female teachers (96%). When the participants' graduation degree is examined, it is seen that 72% of them have undergraduate degrees. It can be said that most teachers work in elementary school (f = 102) while those who work in independent government or private schools are similar in number. When the experience levels of the study group teachers are examined, those with a maximum experience of 5 years or less (f = 95) constitute the most crowded group while teachers who have worked for 21 years or more (f = 8) remain as minority. Considering the working hours, the majority of the participants (82%) work for 40 hours or less while 18% of them work more than 40 hours. When the number of students in the classes of the participants is examined, it is seen that the biggest group (64%) was 11-20 children. Only 4% of the teachers in the study group stated that they have a class size of 31 and above. When asked whether they wanted to work in

another profession or not, 2/3 of the participants said they did not while remaining participants stated that they wanted to pursue another profession.

2.3 Data Collection Tools

2.3.1 Personal Information Form

In order to gather information about teachers in the study, a personal information form was created via Google Forms containing various variables of teachers such as gender, graduation degree, years of experience, desire for a career change, class size, weekly working hours, types of educational institutions.

2.3.2 Vocational Alienation Scale for Pre-school Teachers (VAS-PT)

The “Pre-school Teachers Vocational Alienation Scale” used within the scope of the study was developed by Kırkı (2013). The items of the 5-point Likert-type scale are answered with the options of “Strongly Agree,” “Agree,” “Not Sure,” “Disagree” and “Absolutely Disagree.” The scale consists of 69 items and a total of 5 sub-dimensions which are “*Meaninglessness*” (17 items), “*Sense of Isolation*” (17 items), “*Self-Alienation*” (16 items), “*Powerlessness*” (13 items) and “*Normlessness*” (6 items). The reliability coefficients of the items in the scale are between 0.82 and 0.97, factor load values between 0.42 and 0.87, and item-total correlations ranged from 0.21 to 0.73. There is no reverse coded item in the scale. A minimum of 69 points and a maximum of 345 points can be taken from the scale. The reliability coefficient of the overall scale is .96.

2.3.3 Organizational Climate Scale (OCS)

The “Organizational Climate Scale” used in the study was developed by Hoy and Tarter (1997), and the adaptation of the scale into Turkish was conducted by Yılmaz and Altınkurt (2013). The items of the 4-Likert-type scale are answered with “rarely” (1 point), “sometimes” (2 points), “usually” (3 points) and “very often” (4 points). The scale consists of 39 items. In the scale, there are a total of 6 sub-dimensions which are “Supportive Principal Behavior” (9 items), “Commanding Principal Behavior” (7 items), “Restrictive Principal Behavior” (5 items), “Intimate Teacher Behavior” (7 items), “Collaborative Teacher Behavior among Colleagues” (7 items) and “Disengaged Teacher Behavior” (4 items). The reliability coefficients of the items in the scale are between 0.70 and 0.89, factor load values between 0.46 and 0.82, and item-total correlations ranged from 0.35 to 0.77. Two items in the scale are reverse coded. A minimum of 39 points and a maximum of 156 points can be obtained from the scale.

2.3.4 Self-Efficacy Beliefs Scale for Pre-school Teachers (SEBS-PT)

The “Self-Efficacy Beliefs Scale for Preschool Teachers” used within the scope of the study was developed by Tepe and Demir (2012). The items of the 5-point Likert-type scale are selected with the options of “none” (1 point), “little” (2 points), “moderate” (3 points), “highly” (4 points), and “absolutely” (5 points). The scale consists of 37 items and a total of 6 sub-dimensions which are Teaching Learning Process (9 items), Communication Skills (7 items), Family Participation (5 items), Planning (5 items), Arranging Learning Environments (5 items) and Classroom Management (5 items). The reliability coefficients of the items in the scale are between 0.87 and 0.9, factor load values between 0.67 and 0.89 and item-total correlations ranged from 0.49 to 0.63. There is no reverse coded item in the scale. A minimum of 37 points and a maximum of 185 points can be obtained from the scale. The reliability coefficient of the overall scale is .97.

2.4 Data Collection

A form was created via Google Forms to include the items of Personal Information Form, OCS, VAS-PT, and SEBS-PT. “Mandatory” sign has been added to each question so that they are all filled in. The filling-in duration of the form is about 12-15 minutes. The link to the form created in the data collection process was shared with pre-school teachers through social networks on the internet. The data was collected in this way when pre-school teachers filled in the online form. A total of 227 pre-school teachers answered the questions and all of the forms were included in the study. The process of all teachers filling in the form lasted about one and half months.

2.5 Data Analysis

Quantitative methods were used in analyzing the data. The primary step was to calculate the reliability coefficients of the scales used in the study. In studies in education, a reliability coefficient of 0.70 and above is seen as sufficient in ensuring the reliability of the test (Büyüköztürk, 2010). In this study, the reliability coefficients of the OCS, VAS-PT and SEBS-PT scores are in the range of 0.73-0.82, 0.75-0.92 and 0.82-0.90, respectively. The results show that the scales collected within the scope of the research are reliable.

The averages of the responses of the participants to the three scales, both in the total of the scale and in its sub-factors, were calculated through the SPSS 20.0 program. T-test was used in comparing paired groups, and ANOVA was used for comparing three or more groups. Normality tests were applied for both analyses, and it was concluded that this assumption was not violated. Equations of variances for ANOVA were evaluated with Levene's test. In cases assumption was maintained, Tukey HSD test was used for Post-Hoc or otherwise Dunnett C was used. Pearson's correlation coefficient was used to determine the relationships between variables. While interpreting the coefficients, values lower than 0.30 are classified as "low level relationship," values in the range of 0.30-0.70 as "moderate relationship" and finally, values higher than 0.70 as "high level relationship" (Büyüköztürk, 2010).

3. Results

In this study, correlation coefficients were calculated in order to examine the relationship between pre-school teachers' level of vocational alienation and their perceptions of organizational climate and self-efficacy beliefs. Significance level of these coefficients were also given in Table 2. When looking at the relationship between all sub-dimensions of VAS-PT and OCS, there were significant relationships.

Moderately negative significant relationships were determined between all sub-dimensions scores of VAS-PT and "Supportive Principle Behavior," "Intimate Teacher Behavior" and "Collaborative Teacher Behavior among Colleagues" sub-dimensions scores of Organizational Climate Scale. Relationships between "Disengaged Teacher Behavior" and "Restrictive Principle Behavior" sub-dimensions of Organizational Climate Scale and all sub-dimensions of VAS-PT were significant moderately positive. However, there was no significant relationship between the scores of "Commanding Principle Behavior" sub-dimension and the scores of VAS-PT.

When the correlation coefficients between VAS-PT and the sub-dimensions of SEBS-PT were examined, negative and low-level significant relationships were found between "Sense of Isolation," "Powerlessness" and "Meaninglessness" VAS-PT sub-dimensions and all sub-dimensions of SEBS-PT. Negative and low-level significant relationship was determined between "Self-Alienation" VAS-PT sub-dimension and "Arranging Learning Environments" SEBS-PT sub-dimension. Also, negative and low-level significant relationships were found between "Normlessness" VAS-PT sub-dimension and "Family Participation," "Planning," "Arranging Learning Environments" and "Classroom Management" SEBS-PT sub-dimensions (Table 2).

Table 2. Correlation Coefficients among the all sub-dimensions of the VAS-PT, the OCS and the SEBS-PT

		Sense of Isolation	Self-Alienation	Powerlessness	Normlessness	Meaninglessness
Organizational Climate Scale Sub-dimensions	Supportive Principle Behavior	-.42**	-.38**	-.59**	-.50**	-.51**
	Commanding Principle Behavior	.07	.06	.14	0.08	0.13
	Intimate Teacher Behavior	-.59**	-.41**	-.50**	-.32**	-.44**
	Disengaged Teacher Behavior	.36**	.33**	.34**	.31**	.34**
	Restrictive Principle Behavior	.35**	.41**	.50**	.47**	.48**
	Collaborative Teacher Behavior	-.58**	-.49**	-.56**	-.40**	-.46**

		Between Colleagues				
Self-Efficacy Beliefs Scale	Teaching Learning Processes	-.27**	-.06	-.27**	-.12	-.29**
	Communication Skills	-.25**	-.06	-.22**	-.09	-.28**
	Family Participation	-.28**	-.10	-.29**	-.15*	-.30**
	Planning	-.24**	-.09	-.23**	-.15*	-.27**
	Arranging Learning Environments	-.29**	-.16*	-.26**	-.19**	-.30**
	Classroom Management	-.23**	-.13	-.25**	-.14*	-.27**

* p<0.05 ** p<0.01

T-test and ANOVA analyzes were used to determine the relationship between teachers' level of vocational alienation and variables such as gender, graduation degree, years of experience, desire for a career change, class size, weekly working hours and type of institution.

For both t-test and ANOVA analyzes, whether the groups showed normal distribution was examined by normality tests and histograms. As a result of these examinations, it was determined that normality of the groups was not violated. Homogeneity of variances were examined through the Levene's Test before ANOVA tests. In the selection of post-hoc tests, Tukey HSD was preferred if the variances were assumed equal, whereas Dunnett C test was preferred in case of unequal variances.

Preschool teachers' scores on Sense of Isolation, Self-Alienation, Powerlessness, Normlessness and Meaninglessness VAS-PT sub-dimensions and total score they got from the overall scale do not show a significant difference according to gender variable (Table 3). Although there was a difference in favor of women, this difference was not significant according to the descriptive statistics results. This result was interpreted as the gender variable did not make a significant difference in the sub-dimensions of VAS-PT and throughout the scale.

Table 3. T-test results of Effect of Gender on the VAS-PT

	Gender	n	M	SD	df	t	p
Sense of Isolation	Female	218	2.23	.66	225	.75	.45
	Male	9	2.06	.66			
Self-Alienation	Female	218	3.04	.55	225	1.08	.28
	Male	9	2.84	.43			
Powerlessness	Female	218	2.14	.77	225	1.30	.19
	Male	9	1.79	.89			
Normlessness	Female	218	2.98	.75	225	1.42	.16
	Male	9	2.61	.95			
Meaninglessness	Female	218	2.04	.60	225	-.17	.86
	Male	9	2.08	.98			
Total	Female	218	2.42	.55	225	.92	.36
	Male	9	2.24	.72			

When graduation degrees variable was examined, ANOVA analysis results showed that there was no significant mean differences between the teachers' scores in the "Self-Alienation" VAS-PT sub-dimension, $F(3, 223) = 2.33$, $p > .05$ (Table 4). However there was a significant difference among graduation degrees of the teachers in scores of "Sense of Isolation" VAS-PT sub-dimension, $F(3, 223) = 5.44$, $p < .001$. Tukey HSD test showed that mean scores of graduate graduates ($M = 2.70$) on "Insulation" VAS-PT sub-dimension was statistically higher than scores of high school ($M = 2.01$), associate degree ($M = 2.07$) and undergraduate ($M = 2.19$) graduates.

Results showed that there was a significant mean difference among graduate levels by the preschool teachers' scores on "Powerlessness" sub-dimension, $F(3, 223) = 3.34$, $p < .05$. Mean scores of postgraduate degrees ($M = 2.57$)

was statistically higher than high school ($M = 1.84$) and associate degree ($M = 2.00$) graduates according to post-hoc tests.

ANOVA results of “Normlessness” VAS-PT sub-dimension revealed that there were statistically significant differences among different graduation degrees of teachers, $F(3, 223) = 7.12$, $p < .001$. Scores of bachelor’s degree ($M = 2.99$) graduates in this sub-dimension was statistically higher than the scores of associate degree ($M = 2.60$) graduates. Furthermore, the scores of postgraduate degree ($M = 3.43$) graduates were statistically higher than high school ($M = 2.48$), associate degree ($M = 2.60$) and bachelor’s degree ($M = 2.99$) graduates.

Results showed that there was a significant difference among degrees of graduation of the teachers in terms of the scores “meaninglessness” sub-dimension of VAS-PT, $F(3, 223) = 3.30$, $p < .05$. Post-hoc results showed that postgraduate ($M = 2.37$) degree graduates had statistically high scores compared to high school graduates ($M = 1.73$). Moreover, there was a significant difference among teachers' total scores of VAS-PT, $F(3, 223) = 5.15$, $p < .01$. Postgraduate degree graduates ($M = 2.74$) got higher scores than high school ($M = 2.12$), associate degree ($M = 2.27$) and bachelor’s degree ($M = 2.40$) graduates.

Table 4. ANOVA Results of Effect of Graduation Degrees of Preschool Teachers on the VAS-PT

Scale	Graduation Degree	n	M	SD	F	p	Post-Hoc *
Sense of Isolation	High School	9	2.01	0.47	5.44	.00	1 – 4 2 – 4 3 – 4
	Associates	31	2.07	0.57			
	Bachelor’s	163	2.19	0.62			
	Postgraduate	24	2.70	0.83			
Self-Alienation	High School	9	2.75	0.74	2.33	.08	
	Associates	31	2.93	0.53			
	Bachelor’s	163	3.03	0.53			
	Postgraduate	24	3.24	0.56			
Powerlessness	High School	9	1.84	0.44	3.34	.02	1 – 4 2 – 4
	Associates	31	2.00	0.74			
	Bachelor’s	163	2.10	0.77			
	Postgraduate	24	2.57	0.88			
Normlessness	High School	9	2.48	0.52	7.17	.00	1 – 4 2 – 3 2 – 4 3 – 4
	Associates	31	2.60	0.52			
	Bachelor’s	163	2.99	0.74			
	Postgraduate	24	3.43	0.90			
Meaninglessness	High School	9	1.73	0.40	3.30	.02	1 – 4
	Associates	31	1.95	0.60			
	Bachelor’s	163	2.03	0.57			
	Postgraduate	24	2.37	0.86			
Total	High School	9	2.12	0.43	5.15	.00	1 – 4 2 – 4 3 – 4
	Associates	31	2.27	0.51			
	Bachelor’s	163	2.40	0.53			
	Postgraduate	24	2.78	0.68			

* 1- High School Degree, 2-Associates Degree, 3-Bachelor’s Degree, 4- Postgraduate Degree

When the teachers’ years of experience variable was examined, there was no significant effect of years of experience on teachers’ “Sense of Isolation,” $F(4, 222) = 2.18$, $p > .05$, “Self-Alienation,” $F(4, 222) = .61$, $p > .05$, “Powerlessness,” $F(4, 222) = 1.03$, $p > .05$ and “Normlessness,” $F(4, 222) = .574$, $p > .05$ and “Meaninglessness,” $F(4, 222) = 1.09$, $p > .05$ VAS-PT sub-dimensions scores. As a result, there was no significant difference among seniority

levels of teachers in terms of total scores of teachers got on VAS-PT. Post-hoc tests were not performed since there was no significant difference in both sub-dimensions' and scale total scores.

Table 5. ANOVA Results of Effect of Professional Experiences of the Preschool Teachers on the VAS-PT

Scale	Professional Experience	n	M	SD	F	p
Sense of Isolation	5 years or less	95	2.2	0.59	2.18	0.07
	6-10 years	60	2.41	0.71		
	11-15 years	42	2.04	0.63		
	16-20 years	22	2.13	0.72		
	21 years or more	8	2.31	0.70		
Self-Alienation	5 years or less	95	2.97	0.51	0.61	0.65
	6-10 years	60	3.09	0.57		
	11-15 years	42	3.10	0.55		
	16-20 years	22	3.00	0.63		
	21 years or more	8	3.00	0.56		
Powerlessness	5 years or less	95	2.11	0.78	1.03	0.39
	6-10 years	60	2.27	0.80		
	11-15 years	42	1.99	0.70		
	16-20 years	22	2.11	0.93		
	21 years or more	8	1.89	0.50		
Normlessness	5 years or less	95	2.89	0.76	0.57	0.68
	6-10 years	60	3.06	0.72		
	11-15 years	42	3.00	0.72		
	16-20 years	22	2.88	0.86		
	21 years or more	8	3.10	0.98		
Meaninglessness	5 years or less	95	2.00	0.58	1.09	0.36
	6-10 years	60	2.19	0.64		
	11-15 years	42	1.99	0.57		
	16-20 years	22	2.01	0.83		
	21 years or more	8	1.94	0.39		
Total	5 years or less	95	2.37	0.52	1.10	0.36
	6-10 years	60	2.54	0.59		
	11-15 years	42	2.35	0.51		
	16-20 years	22	2.36	0.70		
	21 years or more	8	2.35	0.50		

Independent-sample t test scores for the changes between participants who want to work at another job or not revealed that there was a significant differences ($p < .05$) in terms of preschool teachers' overall scores on VAS-PT and its sub-dimensions: "Sense of Isolation," "Self-Alienation," "Powerlessness," "Normlessness," "Meaninglessness." Participants want to work in a different job got statistically higher scores on VAS-PT sub-dimensions and overall scale (Table 6).

Table 6. T-test results of Effect of Preschool Teachers' Desire for a Career Change on the VAS-PT

Scale	Desire for a Career Change	n	M	SD	df	t	p
Sense of Isolation	Yes	78	2.48	0.69	225	4.39	0.000
	No	149	2.09	0.59			

Self-Alienation	Yes	78	3.22	0.54	225	3.76	0.000
	No	149	2.93	0.52			
Powerlessness	Yes	78	2.47	0.76	225	5.01	0.000
	No	149	1.94	0.73			
Normlessness	Yes	78	3.17	0.74	225	3.05	0.002
	No	149	2.85	0.74			
Meaninglessness	Yes	78	2.28	0.69	225	4.31	0.000
	No	149	1.92	0.54			
Total	Yes	78	2.66	0.57	225	5.02	0.000
	No	149	2.28	0.51			

ANOVA results indicated that there was no significant difference in “Sense of Isolation,” $F(3, 223)=.57, p>.05$, “Self-Alienation,” $F(3, 223)=1.13, p>.05$, “Powerlessness,” $F(3, 223)=1.22, p>.05$, “Normlessness,” $F(3, 223)=.36, p>.05$, “Meaninglessness,” $F(3, 223)=1.23, p>.05$, VAS-PT sub dimensions and overall scale by the class size, $F(3, 223)=1.19, p>.05$. Because of no significant differences among groups, post-hoc analysis were not performed.

Table 7. ANOVA Results of Effect of Class Size on the VAS-PT

Scale	Class Size	n	M	SD	F	p
Sense of Isolation	0-10	22	2.27	0.66	0.57	0.63
	11-20	147	2.20	0.63		
	21-30	50	2.25	0.75		
	31 or more	8	2.50	0.71		
Self-Alienation	0-10	22	3.05	0.58	1.13	0.34
	11-20	147	3.02	0.56		
	21-30	50	3.01	0.51		
	31 or more	8	3.38	0.57		
Powerlessness	0-10	22	2.18	0.90	1.22	0.30
	11-20	147	2.09	0.75		
	21-30	50	2.13	0.78		
	31 or more	8	2.63	1.13		
Normlessness	0-10	22	3.05	0.78	0.36	0.79
	11-20	147	2.94	0.75		
	21-30	50	2.97	0.82		
	31 or more	8	3.19	0.69		
Meaninglessness	0-10	22	2.10	0.74	1.23	0.30
	11-20	147	2.04	0.62		
	21-30	50	2.00	0.57		
	31 or more	8	2.44	0.70		
Total	0-10	22	2.46	0.64	1.19	0.31
	11-20	147	2.40	0.54		
	21-30	50	2.40	0.57		
	31 or more	8	2.77	0.70		

When examining teachers' weekly working hours and their level of vocational alienation, ANOVA results in Table 8 revealed no significant differences among groups in terms of “Sense of Isolation,” $F(2,224)=.258, p>.05$, “Self-Alienation,” $F(2, 224)=.775, p>.05$, “Powerlessness,” $F(2,224)=.089, p>.05$, “Normlessness,” $F(2, 224)=.85,$

$p > .05$, “Meaninglessness,” $F(2,224)=1.513$, $p > .05$, VAS-PT sub dimensions and overall scale, $F(2, 224)=.231$, $p > .05$.

Table 8. ANOVA Results of Effect of Weekly Working Hours of the Preschool Teachers on the VAS-PT

Scale	Weekly Working Hours	n	M	SD	F	p
Sense of Isolation	20-30 hours	133	2.20	0.67	0.26	0.77
	31-40 hours	54	2.26	0.69		
	41 hours or more	40	2.27	0.59		
Self-Alienation	20-30 hours	133	3.02	0.51	0.78	0.46
	31-40 hours	54	3.11	0.70		
	41 hours or more	40	2.98	0.44		
Powerlessness	20-30 hours	133	2.11	0.77	0.09	0.92
	31-40 hours	54	2.13	0.83		
	41 hours or more	40	2.17	0.79		
Normlessness	20-30 hours	133	3.02	0.76	0.85	0.43
	31-40 hours	54	2.93	0.85		
	41 hours or more	40	2.85	0.64		
Meaninglessness	20-30 hours	133	1.99	0.61	1.51	0.22
	31-40 hours	54	2.09	0.64		
	41 hours or more	40	2.18	0.63		
Total	20-30 hours	133	2.39	0.56	0.23	0.79
	31-40 hours	54	2.45	0.63		
	41 hours or more	40	2.45	0.51		

The last variable in which differentiation according to the level of vocational alienation was examined is the type of school that teachers work in. There were no significant differences among groups according to “Sense of Isolation,” $F(2, 224)=.52$, $p > .05$, “Self-Alienation,” $F(2, 224)=.91$, $p > .05$, “Powerlessness,” $F(2, 224)=1.03$, $p > .05$, “Normlessness,” $F(2, 224)=.36$, $p > .05$, “Meaninglessness,” $F(2, 224)=1.60$, $p > .05$ VAS-PT sub dimensions and overall scale, $F(2, 224)=.80$, $p > .05$. Post hoc tests were not performed as there were no significant differences between the groups.

Table 9. ANOVA Results of Effect of School Type on the VAS-PT

Scale	School Type	n	M	SD	F	p
Sense of Isolation	State Kindergarten	102	2.18	0.64	0.52	0.60
	State Independent Kindergarten	63	2.23	0.71		
	Private Kindergarten	62	2.29	0.62		
Self-Alienation	State Kindergarten	102	3.01	0.52	0.91	0.40
	State Independent Kindergarten	63	3.11	0.54		
	Private Kindergarten	62	2.98	0.59		
Powerlessness	State Kindergarten	102	2.00	0.77	1.03	0.36
	State Independent Kindergarten	63	2.16	0.80		
	Private Kindergarten	62	2.22	0.77		
Normlessness	State Kindergarten	102	2.92	0.79	0.36	0.70

	State	Independent	63	3.02	0.74		
	Kindergarten						
	Private Kindergarten		62	2.97	0.72		
	State Kindergarten		102	1.97	0.61		
Meaninglessness	State	Independent	63	2.08	0.62	1.60	0.20
	Kindergarten						
	Private Kindergarten		62	2.14	0.62		
	State Kindergarten		102	2.36	0.56		
Total	State	Independent	63	2.45	0.56	0.80	0.45
	Kindergarten						
	Private Kindergarten		62	2.46	0.55		

4. Discussion

The study aimed to analyze the factors affecting the level of pre-school teachers' vocational alienation. In this regard, the correlation coefficients between self- efficacy and organizational climate levels and vocational alienation were calculated. As a result of these analyses, moderately significant negative relationships were determined between all sub-dimensions of the VAS-PT and the "Supportive Principal Behavior," "Intimate Teacher Behavior" and "Collaborative Teacher Behavior between Colleagues" sub-dimensions of the OCS. In addition, it is seen that there are moderately positive significant relationships between "Careless Teacher" and "Restrictive Principal Behavior" sub-dimensions of OCS and all the sub-dimensions of VAS-PT. No significant relationship was found between the VAS-PT sub-dimensions and "Commanding Principal Behavior" the OCS sub-dimension. These results indicated that pre-school teachers whose principal is open to suggestions and makes constructive criticism in their institutions and whose colleagues are socially strong and collaborative demonstrate low-level of vocational alienation. In addition, it can be concluded that unnecessary workload and colleagues who give negative criticism increase their level of vocational alienation. Similar to the findings of the study, Witt (1992) pointed out that the organizational climate is an important factor in the formation and development of employees' vocational alienation (as cited in Çalışır, 2006).

When the relationship between the scores of vocational alienation and self-efficacy scores was examined, negative and low-level significant relationships were found between VAS-PT sub-dimensions of "Sense of Isolation," "powerlessness" and "meaninglessness" and all sub-dimensions of Self- Efficacy Scale. In addition, a negative and low-level significant relationship was found between the "self-alienation" sub-dimension and the "arranging learning environments" sub-dimension while negative and low-level significant relationships were also found between the sub-dimension of "normlessness" and "family participation," "planning," "organization of learning environments," and "classroom management" Self-Efficacy Scale sub-dimensions. These meaningful relationships overlap with the findings of Arslan (2017)'s study. According to Arslan (2017), there is a relationship between pre-school teacher's collective self-efficacy levels and perceptions of profession. In general, as the self-efficacy levels of teachers increase, their level of vocational alienation decreases; and as the level of self- efficacy decreases, the level of vocational alienation increases. Accordingly, it can be said that increasing the theoretical knowledge and skills of pre-school teachers through seminars and workshops that will increase their competence in subjects such as learning teaching process, communication skills, family participation, planning, arranging learning environments and classroom management will reduce their level of vocational alienation.

T-test and ANOVA parametric tests were used to determine the relationship between categorical variables such as gender, graduation degree, experience, desire for a career change, class size, weekly working hours, institution type and level of vocational alienation. Considering the graduation degree variable of pre-school teachers, it was seen that there was a significant difference between the mean scores of the VAS-PT sub-dimensions: "sense of isolation," "powerlessness," "normlessness," and "meaninglessness." No significant difference was found between the scores they got from the self-alienation sub-dimension. In these four sub-dimensions, it was determined that those who hold graduate degrees generally score higher than undergraduate, associate degree or high school graduates. On the other hand, in the self-alienation sub-dimension, no significant difference was found between

graduation groups. Different from these results, Kıhrı (2013) did not reach a significant difference in Sense of Isolation, powerlessness and normlessness dimensions in her study, while she reached significant differences against the postgraduate group in meaningfulness and self-alienation scores. A significant difference was found between the levels of pre-school teachers' total VAS-PT scores in terms of the graduation degrees of the teachers. This difference shows that the graduate group is statistically more than those who hold high school degree, associate degree or undergraduate degree. Korkmaz (2014) indicated in his study that undergraduate graduates felt themselves weaker, more meaningless and more isolated than those with a graduate degree, and this was also the case with the total score of the scale. This finding is not in line with the findings of the current study. In the findings of the current study, it is seen that those with higher graduation degree are more alienated from the profession. While the graduate education of teachers creates a more idealistic perspective towards their students and their development, it can be thought that the disagreement with other colleagues, administrators and parents in practice distances them from the profession. Consequently, when the participants were asked in this study whether they would like to work in a different job, the majority stated that they would. However, one-on-one or focus group studies should be conducted with pre-school teachers in order to understand this issue in more depth.

It is observed that there is no significant difference between the scores of pre-school teachers obtained from the total VAS-PT in terms of the duration of the years they worked. This finding is similar to the work of Kıhrı (2013), Korkmaz (2014), Celep (2008), and Çalışır (2006) and contradicts the findings of Elma (2003).

There is no significant difference in terms of gender between pre-school teachers' scores on the sub-dimensions of "Sense of Isolation," "self-alienation," "powerlessness," "normlessness" and "meaninglessness" and the total score they got from the overall scale. Celep (2008), Elma (2003), and Çalışır (2006) could not find a significant difference in terms of gender between the scores of teachers in the Sense of Isolation dimension, which is similar to the findings of the current study. The studies of Celep (2008) and Elma (2003), which have similar results with the current study, do not show a significant difference in terms of gender in the "Powerless" sub-dimension. However, Çalışır (2006) found a significant difference in terms of gender in this sub-dimension.

Pre-school teachers' scores on the sub-dimensions of sense of isolation, self-alienation, powerlessness, normlessness and meaningfulness and the total score they got from the scale show a significant difference according to whether the participants want to work in a different job. It is observed that the level of vocational alienation of teachers who want to do a different job is significantly high. According to these results, factors alienate teachers from the profession and direct them to a different job. Elimination of these negative factors will contribute positively to teachers' desire to continue their career.

It is observed that there is no significant difference in terms of the variable of type of institution where the teachers work, the weekly working hours and the class size when the levels of the scores that pre-school teachers got from the sub-dimensions of the VAS-PT scale are compared with the overall scale. Although it is thought that the level of vocational alienation will increase in groups with high number of weekly working hours and children in the classroom, neither inferential nor descriptive statistics results support this idea.

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